

CONTENT OF AN INFORMATION SHEET (TO BE ADDED ONTO IF NEEDED):

Project title, project funder, project duration

Name and contact details of those responsible

Privacy policy, legal basis

Types of data

Usage

Third country transfer and information on data security

Storage and access

Storage duration of personal data

Publication

Archiving and re-use

Rights of research participants

Person responsible for compliance with data protection regulations

Responsible for archiving / re-use